

FEATURES OF FUNCTIONAL POLYVALENCE OF THE PROVERBS

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Abstract. This article theoretically explains the features of the functional polyvalence of proverbs. Adverbs corresponding to a complete sentence are characterized by a certain functional purpose, that is, they are a potential multiplier of any speech act, for example, threats, encouragements, justifications, etc. Such a pragmatic function is the main goal paremic units, and it is emphasized that it is considered a unique “pragmeme” - accordingly it is emphasized that ready-made repeating formulas are considered for speech acts.

Key words: pragmeme, proverbial polysemy, functional polyvalence, mini-text, paradigm, systematic-generative, mnemonic-reproductive.

Аннотация. В данной статье теоретически объяснены особенности функциональной поливалентности пословиц. Наречия, соответствующие законченному предложению, характеризуются определенным функциональным назначением, то есть являются потенциальным мультипликатором какого-либо речевого акта, например угрозы, поощрения, оправдания, и т. д. Такая прагматическая функция является основной целью паремических единиц, и подчеркивается, что она считается уникальным «прагмемим» – соответствующим подчеркивается, что для речевых актов рассматриваются готовые повторяющиеся формулы.

Ключевые слова: прагмема, пословичная многозначность, функциональная поливалентность, мини-текст, парадигма, системно-генеративная, мнеморепродуктивная.

The functional polyvalency of Proverbs is their positive quality, expanding their scope of application in different contextual contexts (similarly, possible semantic ambiguity, "proverb polysemy") to help expand the scope of application.

In dictionaries, the widespread practice of grouping Proverbs according to the thematic (or thesaurus) principle cannot be considered adequate to the topic, since, unlike words, the nominative units of the language, their meaning, first of all, are determined by their denotative ratio. Proverbs as a mini-text are distinguished by their meaning, the essence of which is a certain attitude. In this regard, proverbs about the same thematic plan can also

mean completely different meanings, and, conversely, the same semantic invariance can be represented by units of different thematic significance.

Paremic units corresponding to a holistic sentence (proverb, adage, joke, etc.) are characterized by a specific functional purpose in pragmatic terms, that is, potential indicators of certain speech actions, such as threat, stimulation, justification, etc. It can even be said that such pragmatic functions are the main goal of paremic units, which are specific "pragmemes" – ready, repeating formulas for corresponding speech actions.

Of course, not all paremiological units are defined uniformly pragmatically. Some of their types are almost in a sense determined by some kind of attitude, for example: greeting, greeting, cursing and other standard forms.

In this type of proverb, the importance of semantic content (and, accordingly, the level of information content) tends to zero (although in some cases it is possible to deviate from this trend, a certain specificity is observed when observing general information. Proverbs are functionally undefined and unambiguous in the general case, therefore, the level of relevance of the semantic-communicative aspect increases (although the communicative value of this type of proverb is not related to their semantic content. Proverbs, however, are very diverse in terms of their functional definition. Some of them have almost any meaning in their ability to define:

1. If the mouse's prey comes, they get it with the cat (threat).
2. The wall also has an ear (thinking).
3. It's a thousand coins (motivation) to the one who knows.
4. The soul of the ship is one (motivation), etc.

In terms of its production and functioning, the human language will exist in two opposite ways:

On the one hand, it is a generative model based on the regularity and systemality of self-organization.

On the second hand, the reality is a set of communicative fragments based on the memory of native speakers and repeated in speech in a more or less finished form.

Although the corresponding opposite "paradigms" were already known in ancient Greece in the form of discussions between "analogs", they believed that linguistics was the structure and functioning of the linguistic language, until recently linguistics recognized only the first, systematic, structural idea.

The systemic-generative and mnemonic-reproductive components of the linguistic

being dominate and manifest themselves in various aspects and perspectives. The mnemonic nature of the language already dominates in everyday communication, but there is maximum concentration in the application of the language "quote-appeal". The use of paremic linguistic formations (e.g. proverbs and adages) is in this sense a classic form of implementation of the mnemonic-reproductive language model.

To one degree or another, other principles are also associated with the corresponding concepts of logic: consistency, contradiction, meaninglessness, impossibility, equivalence, exception. However, as the organizational basis of paremic units, these concepts differ significantly from each other in strict logic. For example, consistency in logic refers to the consistency of reasoning and logical actions.

Consistency in Proverbs, above all, concerns human behavior: "Think first, then speak". However, it is interesting that the author of logical dictionary, N.I. Kondakov, describes the logical essence of the sequence: The sound comes from the previous idea, of course. The following proverb testifies to our opinion: "whoever says A must say B too."

The importance of the identified principles for the formation of paremic meanings is evidenced by the fact that some of them correspond to the fundamental concepts of logic, which deals with determining the basic laws of human mental activity. These primarily require the principles of necessary condition and sufficient condition. At the same time, it should be remembered that from the point of view of studying proverbs, these principles have their own characteristics, which significantly separate them from the corresponding logical laws. Logically, if they serve to make judgments of truth and thus depend on the real relations between the data of the conceptual content used, these principles play the role of more organizational factors in terms of the formation of paremic units.

So, if there is a head, there would be a neck, and we can find the collar in terms of logic by the formula of sufficient conditions, which are understood as imitations of the corresponding logical form, not truth judgments.

Similarly, in sentences such as lying and betrayal, the necessary condition formula does not ensure the truth of the sentence, but in other cases, proverbs with a similar structure can be considered logically correct, for example, "If a fire goes into the forest, it will burn both wet and dry", "From you that's all, that's all from me."

It is worth noting that proverbs expressed in various cultural and linguistic fields are mainly based on the principle of "sufficient basis". "If the condition A is fulfilled, the consequence B also applies", "If you dig a hole for someone, you yourself will fall", "Where

the big cart goes, the small cart also goes there."

In conclusion, it is worth saying that variant, synonymy and transformation in proverbs are different phenomena. The main difference between them is the content, theme/theme, structural peculiarities.

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